

Effect on Learning and Memory Process in Sub Acute Noise-Stressed Wistar Albino Rats related to Eugenol

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Eugenol (4-allyl-2-methoxyphenol), the principal chemical constituent of clove oil and tulsi has been primarily derived from a variety of plant sources, including *Eugenia caryophyllus*, *Oscimum sanctum* Linn and *Myristica fragran*. Eugenol is a substance that either improves or disrupts the learning and memory processes in animals, a recent trend that has generated considerable interest. **Aim and Objectives-** Eugenol was chosen for this study to determine its effect on learning and memory in Wistar albino rodents with noise-induced memory loss. **Materials and Methods:** Using Wistar strain male albino rats, researchers investigated the impact of Eugenol on Learning and Memory when exposed to Noise Stress **Results:** Compared to the control group, rats treated with Eugenol displayed a greater proportion of accurate responses and a shorter time to attain the goal. Compared to the noise stress-treated group, the Eugenol noise stress-treated group demonstrated an increase in correct responses and a decrease in the time required to attain the goal. This demonstrates that Eugenol exacerbates the memory loss caused by stress in Wistar albino rodents. Even after drug withdrawal, the test rodents demonstrated improved performance. **Conclusion;** This study demonstrates that Eugenol has excellent retention performance. Eugenol was discovered to have antioxidant activity. The current study revealed that Eugenol improves memory in the T-Maze test. Eugenol possesses antioxidant properties and decreased brain acetylcholinesterase enzyme levels, resulting in increased acetylcholine concentration in the brain and enhanced memory in rats exposed to noise stress.

Keywords: Eugenol, Neurogenesis, Memory, Sub Acute Noise-Stressed, Learning.

INTRODUCTION

The brain responsible for the basis for thought, emotion, desire, perception, learning, and memory.¹ Memory is the fundamental mental process, and without it, we are limited to basic reflexes and ingrained behaviors. Learning is the process of acquiring new information, whereas Memory is the process of retaining that knowledge. Three necessary stages in the learning and memory process are encoding, storage, and retrieval.²

Numerous animal species may learn as a consequence of habituation or classical conditioning. Classical conditioning is a robust and effective method for investigating the fundamental learning and memory of animals. A person's spatial memory is necessary for navigating a familiar city, just as a rat's spatial memory is necessary for learning the location of food at the conclusion of a maze.

Hippocampus has a major role in learning and is responsible for spatial memory regulation. Animals are able to construct a spatial map of their environment through the use of reference and working memory. It also regulates long-term and short-term memory as well as spatial navigation, both of which are necessary for the rodent to successfully navigate the maze.³

Stress is a term used to characterize emotionally and physiologically demanding situations. Noise stress increases acetylcholinesterase activity and decreases the number of dendrites in the hippocampus and medial prefrontal cortex. High frequency noise may result in neurologic, vascular, immune, and cardiac disorders.³ It is widely acknowledged that stress can cause brain damage, particularly in the hippocampal formation, but the mechanisms that lead to this damage are poorly understood.⁴ As a result of irritation and stress, noise may also cause health disorders, such as oxidative stress, which is a result of noise exposure over time. Stress entails two-way neural and endocrine communication between the brain and cardiovascular, immune, and other systems.

The brain is a target of stress, and the hippocampus was the first brain region to be identified as a target of glucocorticoids, besides the hypothalamus. Certain brain regions can undergo acute and chronic alterations due to stress, which can result in long-term damage. Memory is typically negatively impacted by excessive stress hormone secretion. The limbic system is the primary region of the brain concerned with stress.

Eugenol is a substance that either improves or disrupts the learning and memory processes in animals, a recent trend that has generated considerable interest. Clove (*Syzygium aromaticum*) is a well-known spice with a distinctive aroma; it contains a high concentration of oil known as clove oil. Eugenol is the primary phytoconstituent of clove oil. Eugenol is reported to be an anti-stress agent.⁵ Clove is the desiccated flower bud of the *Syzygium aromaticum* (Myrtaceae) plant. It is made up of volatile oil (14%-21%), tannin (10%-13%), phenol, sesquiterpene ester, and alcohol. In indigenous medicine, clove and its oil are utilized for their antiseptic, anti-oxidant, analgesic, and

neuroprotective properties. Thus, it attracts a great deal of interest from researchers in the pharmaceutical, food, and cosmetic industries.

Clove has multiple therapeutic properties, including aphrodisiac, stomachic, carminative, nervous stimulant, and tonic, according to its traditional use. Numerous scientific studies have demonstrated its aphrodisiac, antibacterial, antifungal, nematocidal, anti-toothache, anti-oxidant, analgesic, anesthetic, and hypotensive properties.⁶ Although several formulations containing Clove have been used as a nervous stimulant and cognitive enhancer in traditional Iranian medicine, Clove's pharmacological effect on cognitive functions has not been evaluated in detail. ⁷ Eugenol is a phenylpropene, a guaiacol with an allyl chain substitution. Eugenol is a member of the class of chemical compounds known as phenylpropanoids. It is a colorless to pale yellow oily liquid derived from essential oils, particularly clove oil. It is present at 80–90% concentrations in clove bud oil.⁸

It can be utilized to reduce *Listeria monocytogenes* and *Lactobacillus sakei* in food. They are also used in the production of plastics and rubber stabilizers and antioxidants. The use of clove oil as an anesthetic on aquarium fish and on wild fish for research and management purposes is rising in popularity.

In the past, however, cloves, the desiccated flower buds of the tropical tree *Syzygium aromaticum*, were utilized more for food preservation than for flavoring. The 80 to 95 percent of clove oil is eugenol, which is primarily responsible for cloves' ability to prevent food from spoiling. According to research, it also has health benefits for the human body.

Dentists frequently use oil of cloves or eugenol because it is antiseptic and anti-inflammatory. It is frequently applied to the gums to eliminate bacteria and alleviate the discomfort of dental procedures such as tooth extractions, fillings, and root canals. In addition, clove oil, cinnamon oil, basil oil, and nutmeg oil, all of which contain eugenol, are prevalent ingredients in mouthwashes, toothpastes, soaps, insect repellents, perfumes, foods, and various veterinary medications.

In one study, rodents were exposed with carbon tetrachloride, which causes severe oxidative damage to tissues. According to the researchers, rats given eugenol along with carbon tetrachloride were strongly protected from its toxic effects. Internal use of eugenol requires professional supervision. Use of fresh or dried herbs and spices containing eugenol in moderation is a safer method of ingesting eugenol, and even small quantities can provide significant antioxidant benefits.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Using Wistar strain Male albino rats, researchers investigated the impact of Eugenol on Learning and Memory when exposed to Noise Stress. Eugenol was chosen for this study with aim ,to determine its effect on learning and memory in Wistar albino rodents with noise-induced memory loss.All test subjects were fit and weighed between 140 and 180 gms. The animals were raised in the Animal House of the Institute, University of Madras, Taramani, Chennai, India, and all rats were acclimated to the standard conditions and constant ambient temperature with a 12-hour dark photo period. The rats were provided with food (Rat feed, Hindustan Lever Ltd.)

The animals were separated into four groups of three each.

Groups	Description	Experimental design
1.	Control	This group is used to study the base line value of the parameter.
2.	Sub Acute Noise Stress Only	This group has received Sub Acute Noise Stress alone for 15 days.
3.	Drug Treated	This group has treated with Eugenol for 15 days.
4.	Sub Acute Noise Stress and Drug Treated	This group has received Sub Acute noise stress for 15 days and Treated orally with Eugenol for 15 days.

NOISE STRESS PROCEDURE:

A loudspeaker (15W), installed 30 cm above the cage and powered by a white noise generator emitting all frequencies between 0 and 20 kHz, produced the noise. A precise sound level meter was used to calibrate the intensity of the sound in the cage to 100db. During the investigation, the noise level peaked at 100 dB as soon as the generator was turned on and persisted for four hours per day.

ROUTE AND DOSAGE OF EUGENOL

The animals in GROUP III and GROUP IV were administered 200 mg/kg of eugenol. For 15 days, eugenol was dissolved in 1 ml of olive oil and administered intraperitoneally.

SPATIAL MEMORY TESTING - (T-Maze)

A T-maze is a rudimentary maze used in animal cognition experiments in the field of behavioral science. It is shaped like the letter T, allowing the rodent to make a simple decision. Using various stimuli, T-mazes are used to examine the memory and spatial learning abilities of rodents. Beginning in the early 20th century, investigations such as the T-Maze utilized rodents. These concepts of T-mazes are used to evaluate the behavior of rodents. The various tasks, such as left-right discrimination and forced alternation, are primarily used to assess the reference and working memories of rodents.

The rat's spatial memory is responsible for storing information regarding its environment and spatial orientation. This spatial memory enables the rat to navigate the numerous mazes and obstacles presented by the researchers.

This enables the rat to repeatedly navigate the same maze while remembering the correct and incorrect routes. In the T-maze, this is reduced to a single left or right turn, but in more complex mazes, the rat must remember a succession of turns in order to reach its reward. A poor spatial memory can cause a rat to continually get lost in the maze, regardless of how well it has performed in the past.

Spontaneous alternation in rats and mice refers to the rodents' innate tendency to choose alternate arms in a Y- or T-maze. Diverse mechanisms have been ascribed to the operation of spontaneous alternation behavior, but regardless of this ethological function, it is evident that the animal must recall which arm it entered on a previous occasion in order to alternate its choice on a subsequent trial.

Consequently, behavioral pharmacologists have embraced spontaneous alternation as a quick and relatively straightforward measure of spatial working memory, devoid of fear, reward, or reinforcers .

DATA ANALYSIS

The results were reported as the mean plus the standard error of the mean (SEM). One-way analyses of variance (ANOVAs) were applied to the data. When a statistically significant difference was discovered, the Student-Newman-Keuls post-hoc test was performed. A difference was deemed significant in all analyses when $p < 0.05$.

RESULT

The rats treated with noise stress, Eugenol, and both stress and Eugenol remained healthy throughout the duration of the experiment, and none of the groups exhibited any discernible behavioural alterations.

On day 1, all four groups, i.e., control, noise stress-treated, Eugenol-treated, and both noise stress and Eugenol-treated rats, spontaneously alternated at an average rate in successive trials (table 1, 2) as (control, 37%; noise stress-treated, 47%; Eugenol-treated, 50%; Eugenol+ noise treated, 47%).(figure 1-5).

On day 8, control, noise stress-treated, and both noise stress-treated and Eugenol-treated rats spontaneously alternated at a moderate rate and did not demonstrate significant improvement, whereas Eugenol-treated rats demonstrated a slight improvement (normal, 43%; noise stressed, 43%; Eugenol-treated, 60%; Eugenol+ noise-treated, 47%).

On day 15, control groups demonstrated a slight improvement,(53%), noise stress treated groups demonstrated a decrease in spontaneous alternation,(33%), Eugenol treated groups demonstrated a significantly increased rate of spontaneous alternation,(66%), and Eugenol + noise treated groups demonstrated a slight improvement,(56%). On day 22, the control and Eugenol+noise treated groups exhibited an increase in spontaneous alternation (control, 73%; Eugenol+noise treated, 70%), whereas the untreated group exhibited a decrease. Noise stress-treated groups exhibited a low rate of spontaneous alternation (26%), whereas Eugenol-treated groups demonstrated a high rate of spontaneous alternation (80%).(Figure 6-10)

Figure 1:

Figure 2:

Figure 3:

Figure 4

Figure 5:

Figure 6:

Figure 7:

Figure 8:

Effect of Eugenol on Correct Entry in T maze:

The data is summarised with Mean SD in figure 9. Animals exposed to noise stress exhibited no significant change on days 1 and 8, but on days 15 and 22, significant changes were observed when compared to the control group. Compared to the control group, the stress-treated group, and the stress-plus-Eugenol-treated group, animals treated with Eugenol exhibited no significant change on day 1, but significant changes on days 8, 15, and 22. On day one, animals treated with both stress and Eugenol did not differ significantly from the other three groups, but on days eight, fifteen, and twenty-two, they differed significantly from the Eugenol-treated group, the noise-treated group, and the Eugenol-treated group.

Effect of Eugenol on Latency period in T maze

The data is summarized with Mean SD in figure 9. Animals exposed to noise stress exhibited no significant change on days 1 and 8, but on days 15 and 22, significant changes were observed when compared to the control group. Compared to the control group, the stress-treated group, and the stress-plus-Eugenol-treated group, animals treated with Eugenol exhibited no significant change on day 1, but significant changes on days 8, 15, and 22. On day one, animals treated with both stress and Eugenol did not differ significantly from the other three groups, but on days eight, fifteen, and twenty-two, they differed significantly from the Eugenol-treated group, the noise-treated group, and the Eugenol-treated group.

Table 1: Spontaneous alternation in T Maze

S.No	GROUPS	PERCENTAGE OF CORRECT ENTRY			
		DAY 1	DAY 8	DAY 15	DAY22
1	CONTROL	37±2.98	43±2.98	53±2.98	73±2.98
2	STRESS	47±3.94	43±3.94	33±3.94	26±3.94
3	DRUG TREATED	50±3.94	60±3.94	66±3.94	80±3.94
4	STRESS+ DRUG TEATED	47±3.65	47±3.65	56±3.65	70±3.65

Figure 9:

Table 2: Total Time taken to enter the Baited Arm

S.No	GROUPS	TOTAL TIME TAKEN			
		DAY 1	DAY 8	DAY 15	DAY 22
1	CONTROL	40±1.07	35±1.07	28±1.07	17±1.07
2	STRESS	50±1.85	51±1.85	56±1.85	60±1.85
3	DRUG TREATED	27±1.19	24±1.19	16±1.19	16±1.19
4	STRESS+ DRUG TREATED	37±1.23	35±1.23	28±1.23	23±1.23

Figure 10:

DISCUSSION

Working memory is a cognitive function that maintains a small quantity of information in an active state for a brief period of time. 10 Environmental noise affects health and well-being by interfering with fundamental activities such as sleep, rest, communication, concentration, and cognition; it can also result in a general sense of annoyance. 11-14 .

Noise is an environmental stressor that influences behavioral, psychological, and physiological processes. 11,15 Spontaneous Alternation Behavior (SAB), which employs the classic "T" Maze, is an extremely essential type of place recognition task. 16

Stress is a potent modulator of cognitive function in general and learning and memory processes in particular. 17 ,18 Numerous mental disorders can be precipitated by life's stresses. The contemporary way of life causes numerous stressful conditions. Additionally, their prevalence is rising daily. By inhibiting adult neurogenesis or influencing neurochemical systems (such as catecholamines and glucocorticoids), stress may influence learning and memory processes.

Due to the numerous side effects of allopathic drugs used to treat these diseases, the search for alternative treatments continues. Therefore, it is prudent to seek options that are both effective and secure. Indigenous medical practises, including the use of natural botanicals, are a time-tested method of treatment. Herbal medicines emphasise disease prevention, body system rejuvenation, maintaining balance and harmony, and life extension. 19 Due to simple accessibility, low cost, and ancestral knowledge, medicinal herbs are an indispensable component of traditional medicine worldwide. A variety of flora have been utilized for the treatment of mental illness. Eugenol is one of these ingredients.

Memory is affected in numerous ways by stress. Depending on the timing of stress exposure, (hippocampus-dependent) memory processes can be impaired or enhanced (by stress).It has been suggested previously that these effects require simultaneous noradrenergic and glucocorticoid activity in the basolateral amygdala and that the direction of the stress effects on memory depends on whether the stress is experienced

within or outside the context of the learning episode . 20, 21

Acute tension impairs the capacity for learning and memory. The study by Manikandan et al., have demonstrated that acute stress impairs the learning and memory capacities of rodents.²²

In experimental settings, acute noise exposure has been linked to transient increases in blood pressure and levels of stress hormones; therefore, it is hypothesized that long-term noise exposure may have negative effects on health. ²³

Essential oil extracted from desiccated flower buds of clove, *Syzygium aromaticum* L. Merr. and Perry (Myrtaceae), is applied topically to alleviate pain and promote healing. ²⁴ Clove has numerous therapeutic properties, including anti-inflammatory, neuroprotective, antihyperglycemic, nervous stimulant, tonic antimutagenic, aphrodisiac, bactericidal, nematocidal, fungicidal, anti-toothache, antioxidant, analgesic, anaesthetic, and hypotensive. ^{8,22} ,

Eugenol and lesser volumes of beta-caryophyllene and Eugenol acetate make up the majority of the essential oil of *Syzygium aromaticum*. ²⁴

Acute administrations of clove oil improve learning and memory recall and can reverse short-term and long-term memory deficits, according to a number of studies. ^{8, 25}

When rodents avoid a familiar arm of a maze in favour of an unfamiliar arm, spontaneous alternation occurs. It is a working memory-dependent exploration measure. ^{26 ,27}

Tolman et al. (1925) defined spontaneous alteration behavior as the tendency of rats to alternate their selections of T Maze or Y Maze arms at successive opportunities. ²⁸

Additionally, clove oil can be used as a source of natural antioxidants and in pharmaceutical applications.²⁹

Eugenol, the primary component of clove oil, is responsible for many of its antioxidant properties. 30 It possesses substantial antioxidant and cyclooxygenase inhibiting properties. The activity was comparable to that of ibuprofen, naproxen, and aspirin at concentrations of 10, 1,000, and 10,000 microM, respectively. This supports the traditional anti-inflammatory use of *O. sanctum*.31. The magnitude and duration of stress-induced behavioural impairments are dependent on the nature and duration of the adverse experience, as well as the testing paradigm. 18, 32 Typically, elevated corticosterone levels are associated with behavioural alterations associated with stress in rats 33

In this study, the effectiveness of Eugenol in preventing stress-induced memory loss in rats was evaluated. Test rats were administered eugenol intraperitoneally at a dose of 200mg/kg body weight as a single dose for 15 consecutive days and were exposed to noise stress for 4 hours per day with a frequency range of 0-20K Hz and an intensity of 100dB.

It is known that stress causes memory impairment. Neuronal injury in the hippocampal region as a result of excitotoxicity and changes in neurotransmitter levels in the brain regions is the neural basis for this impairment. Alternately, increased glucocorticoids may mediate neuronal injury in this region. The increased oxidative stress and decreased antioxidant defence status in the brain caused by stress may be the cause of memory loss.34 Glucocorticoids are adrenal steroids that are secreted in response to stress and play a crucial role in the stress response.35 Sandi and Pinelo- Navarro (2007) explained that glucocorticoids serve as a common mediator for both the facilitating and impairing effects of stress on various memory processes and phases.36 Among the brain regions implicated in the mediation of stress effects, the hippocampus, amygdala, and prefrontal cortex stand out as crucial.

Increased central noradrenergic activity is associated with impairment of prefrontal cortex functions involved in working memory performance, which may account for the stressed group's lower accuracy.37

Eugenol prevents the noise-induced decrease in total acetylcholine content and increase in the activity of four brain regions, including the hippocampus, in animals. 8

All groups of rats were initially taught in the T maze. At the conclusion of each week, both test rats and control rats were evaluated based on the number of correct responses out of 10 trials for spontaneous modification and latency period to reach the target area.

Animals are able to perform well in post period because rehearsal performance is stored in the form of information in their working memory. In contrast, the hippocampus is impaired in the noise stressed group, altering the memory performance of these individuals. Compared to the control and acute noise stress treated rats, rats treated with Eugenol exhibited a higher proportion of correct responses to reach the goal. In the acute noise stress treated group, spatial learning ability is impaired, which may be due to noise-induced damage to the hippocampus.

In rats administered Eugenol, there was an increase in the proportion of correct responses and a decrease in the time required to attain the target. This demonstrates Eugenol's memory-enhancing properties. After 7 days of drug cessation, rats treated with Eugenol demonstrated a high proportion of correct responses and a decreased latency period relative to the control group. Eugenol is an exceptional antioxidant source; it has a positive effect on performance retention.

CONCLUSION

Compared to the control group, rats treated with Eugenol displayed a greater proportion of accurate responses and a shorter time to attain the goal. Compared to the noise stress-treated group, the Eugenol noise stress-treated group demonstrated an increase in correct responses and a decrease in the time required to attain the goal. This demonstrates that Eugenol exacerbates the memory loss caused by stress in Wistar albino rodents. Even after drug withdrawal, the test rodents demonstrated improved performance. This demonstrates that Eugenol has excellent retention performance. Eugenol was discovered to have antioxidant activity. The current study revealed that Eugenol improves memory in the T-Maze test. Eugenol possesses antioxidant properties and decreased brain acetylcholinesterase enzyme levels, resulting in increased acetylcholine concentration in the brain and enhanced memory in rats exposed to noise stress.

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